

TECHNOLOGIES AND TOOLS THAT ENCOURAGE COLLABORATION AMONG
LEARNERS

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ANNOTATION

The article discusses the content of the organization of the educational process based on collaborative learning, the establishment of cooperative relations between teachers, administration and students and teachers' organizations, leaders, parents, the public. Went Factors for the development of student learning motivation using collaborative technology and the achievement of high results through the implementation of the principles of humanization of the educational process are identified.

Keywords: Collaborative learning, socio-psychological environment, collaborative relationships, education, team teaching, small group teaching, independent thinking.

R. Slavin, one of the authors of the collaborative learning technology, noted that it is not enough to give students instructions to complete tasks together. It is necessary for students to have real cooperation, to rejoice in the success achieved by each student, to sincerely help each other, and to create a favorable socio-psychological environment. In this technology, when determining the quality of students' mastery of knowledge, they are compared not with each other, but with the daily result of each student with the previously achieved result. Only then, realizing that the result achieved during the lesson benefits the team, students feel responsible and strive to learn more, master knowledge, skills and competencies.

In collaborative pedagogy, the student is considered as the subject of his own educational activity. In this case, the teacher and the student are equal as subjects of the pedagogical process, and a process of cooperative pedagogy is formed. They become partners, friends, co-creators, co-participants, sympathizers, and co-managers. Cooperative relations are also established between teachers, between the administration and students and teacher organizations, between leaders, parents, and the public. Cooperative teaching technologies are formed on the basis of cooperative pedagogy, which differs from traditional pedagogy in the following ways: In traditional education, the teacher is considered the subject of the pedagogical process, and the student is considered the object.

Cooperative teaching ensures the achievement of high results by developing the student's motivation for learning and implementing the principles of humanizing the educational process.

Collaborative learning allows you to achieve the following results:

- enriches the student's learning process;
- provides students with a set of cognitive information that is shared and mastered among them;
- arouses students' interest in learning the material;
- expands students' opportunities to form their own knowledge and worldview;
- increases the effectiveness of two-way information exchange;
- provides students with the necessary knowledge to prepare for independent life;
- promotes positive interactions between different cultural and socio-economic groups.

Most of these types of activities involve dividing students into small groups, assigning them roles and tasks. This takes into account the following. Collaborative learning technologies are based on

improving the pedagogical process and directing it to the individual student. These technologies serve to create a creative environment aimed at forming a creative personality, to increase the quality and efficiency of learning [1-30].

The main processes of collaborative learning include: collaborative exchange of ideas, conversation, analysis, discussion, negotiation, practical tasks, seeing something, making, solving problems, etc. When organizing collaborative learning sessions: teacher-class, teacher-small group. Teacher-large group, teacher-student, student-student (working in pairs), small group, group-class and other organizational forms are used. Collaborative learning is a popular expression that describes the instructional and interactive processes in which the teacher organizes effective cooperation with a group of students, an individual student and the whole class in the educational process, as well as the implementation of mutually supportive cooperation of students. Students work collaboratively on academic assignments, in small groups, and help each other and their peers.

In general, collaborative learning methods have the following five characteristics:

1. Students work together on a common task or learning activity, which is best learned through group work.
2. Students work together in small groups of 2-5 members.
3. Students follow socially accepted behavioral criteria developed by the group to achieve a common task or to carry out a learning activity.
4. Students are positive and independent. The organization of work on a common task or learning activity is designed to take into account the need for students to help each other.
5. Students are personally responsible and accountable for their work, or in other words, for studying, learning.

Some non-traditional lesson forms implemented by collaborative learning technologies

Press conference lesson - an exercise in mastering the topic of the lesson through questions and answers.

The lesson of the club of the cheerful, clever - an exercise in teaching independent thinking by finding interesting questions and answers to them.

Group work lesson - an exercise in consolidating knowledge by organizing students to perform tasks in several groups.

Mutual teaching lesson - a lesson in mastering the topic by organizing students to explain to each other certain paragraphs of the text or similar small fragments of the lesson content. Student-led lesson - an exercise in increasing student activity by organizing students to explain the topic of the lesson.

Competition lesson - a lesson in organizing a competition of students in the class on one or more topics with prior preparation, and determining the winners. Pair work (binary) lesson - a lesson in which students work in pairs to master the topic of the lesson together or to consolidate each other's knowledge. If necessary, pairs can be changed during the lesson.

Dialogue lesson - consists of exercises to explain and consolidate the topic of the lesson by organizing dialogues with students in order to teach students to think independently and develop their skills in expressing their thoughts. Circle exercise lesson - consists of exercises to master a new topic or to repeat and consolidate the lesson based on the turn-by-turn participation of students.

Innovation lesson - a lesson to introduce proposals and projects on the introduction of innovations in the field of academic subjects or related to school life, as well as the practical application of the results

of students' creative activities, which serves to increase students' knowledge and develop their creative abilities. The main idea of cooperative learning is not only to complete learning tasks together, but also to learn to learn together.

Team learning (R. Slavin) In team learning, students are divided into two teams of equal size. Both teams perform the same task. Team members complete learning tasks together, focusing on each student mastering the knowledge, skills, and competencies provided for in the topic. R. Slavin noted that it is not enough to give students instructions for completing tasks together. It is necessary to create literal cooperation between students, a sense of joy at the success achieved by each student, a sense of sincere help for each other, and a favorable socio-psychological environment. In this technology, when determining the quality of students' mastery of knowledge, they are compared not with each other, but with the daily results of each student with the results previously achieved. Only then will students, realizing that the results they achieve during the lesson will benefit the team, feel responsible, strive to research more, and thoroughly master knowledge, skills, and competencies.

Collaborative teaching in small groups In this method, small groups are formed of 4 students. The teacher first explains the topic, then organizes independent work of the students. The learning tasks are divided into four parts, and each student completes a certain part of the task. At the end of the task, each student reflects on the part he or she completed and teaches his or her classmates, and then the group members draw a general conclusion about the task. The teacher listens to the information of each small group and controls and evaluates knowledge using test questions.

Specific pedagogical, psychological and methodological foundations for the effective use of collaborative learning technologies have been developed, which are as follows:

- organizational and pedagogical foundations - determining and implementing conditions and opportunities for collaborative work of participants in the training session based on the curriculum, program, lesson topic, DTS requirements and the volume of new knowledge required to be mastered in accordance with them;
- psychological foundations - taking into account the psychological and age characteristics of students, creating a favorable psychological environment for each student in the training session, ensuring that the topic, content of the lesson, concepts, terms, definitions, formulas and other conditions used are understandable to students in the quality organization of free communication;
- methodological foundations - preparing the necessary tools for the training session in advance, ensuring their quality at the required level.

The purpose of collaborative learning activities is to create a mechanism for managing the mastered activity and joint actions, attitudes and communication. The product of collaborative activity is the emergence of new ideas put forward by students and goals related to the essence of the activity being mastered, as well as the desire to manage the position of the individual in partnership. By the method of collaborative activity, one should understand the system of joint actions of the teacher and the student. Such actions begin with the teacher's assistance to the student, the activity of the students gradually increases and turns into practical and intellectual actions that are completely controlled by them, and the relationship between the teacher and the student acquires the character of a partnership position.

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